

SOCIAL LIFE AND SPEECH

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Annotation

The article deals with social life and speech. About these each other connected verbal communications.

Keywords

Speech, social life, totality, discipline, realization, need.

Social life is a set of diverse types and forms of joint activity of people aimed at providing conditions and means of subsistence, the realization of needs, interests, values. The main feature of social life is its joint ...

Social life should also be considered from the side of those properties and forms that do not manifest themselves in public or are weak, having a "hidden" social character, for example, the direct (natural) and personal (private) life of a person. The point is that, like all other processes and forms of social life, social life is at the same time a manifestation and provision of the immediate life that flows in individuals. People, living a social life, simultaneously live their immediate life, spending their own energy, nerves, and health on social life.

Therefore, social life is thoroughly saturated with the processes and relationships associated with the implementation, production and reproduction of this immediate life. And since this process, as is known, is of two kinds (on the one hand, the production of means of subsistence, on the other, the production of man himself, the procreation), social life ultimately obeys the laws not only of the first, but also of the second. True, here it takes the form of personal (private), including family, life, characterized by such a type of compatibility, which, as a rule, is extremely individualized and does not exist without being isolated from society.

Thus, social life is the joint life activity of people, which implies their mutual dependence and need for each other and ensures the preservation and development of the social organism. This is the life of people directly in a team, a social group, where joint activities, communication, exchange of services, use of common things and values are carried out. This is life within the framework of collectively developed stereotypes of behavior, social discipline, social prescriptions, impersonal norms that require appropriate reactions and actions.

Creating their social life, people at the same time create social relations within which it is realized.

Speech is a historically established form of communication between people through language structures created on the basis of certain rules. The process of speech involves, on the one hand, the formation and formulation of thoughts by language (speech) means, and on the other hand, the perception of language structures and their understanding.

The most important achievement of man, which allowed him to use universal human experience, both past and present, was speech communication, which developed on the basis of labor activity. Speech is language in action. Language is a system of signs that includes words with their meanings plus syntax - a set of rules by which sentences are built. The word is a kind of sign, since the latter are present in various kinds of formalized languages.

The objective property of a verbal sign, which determines theoretical activity, is the meaning of the word, which is the relation of the sign (the word in this case) to the object designated in reality, regardless (abstractly) of how it is represented in individual consciousness.

Unlike the meaning of a word, personal meaning is a reflection in the individual consciousness of the place that a given object (phenomenon) occupies in the system of activity of a particular person. If the meaning unites the socially significant features of the word, then the personal meaning is the subjective experience of its content.

The following main functions of the language are distinguished:

- a means of subsistence, transmission and assimilation of socio-historical experience
- means of communication (communications)
- an instrument of intellectual activity (perception, memory, thinking, imagination)

Performing the first function, the language serves as a means of encoding information about the studied properties of objects and phenomena. Through language, information about the surrounding world and the person himself, received by previous generations, becomes the property of subsequent generations. Performing the function of a means of communication, the language allows you to influence the interlocutor directly (if we directly indicate what needs to be done) or indirectly (if we inform him of information that is important for his activities, which he will focus on immediately or at another time in the appropriate situations).

Speech is an essential element of human activity, allowing a person to learn about the world around him, to transfer his knowledge and experience to other people, to accumulate them for transmission to subsequent generations.

Being a means of expressing thoughts, speech, in the course of its development in ontogenesis, becomes the main (but not the only) mechanism of human thinking. Higher, abstract thinking is impossible without speech activity.

I.P. Pavlov noted that only speech activity gives a person the opportunity to abstract from reality and generalize, which is a distinctive feature of human thinking.

Depending on the form of communication, speech activity is divided into oral (implying speaking and listening) and written (writing and reading).

In the course of "productive" types of speech activity - speaking and writing - the following main groups of mental and physiological mechanisms are involved:

- a mechanism for programming a speech statement, conveyed meaning.
- a group of mechanisms associated with the construction of the grammatical structure of an utterance, the search for the right words by semantic features, the choice of a specific sound (in oral speech, see speech sound, phoneme) or graphic system (in written speech, see grapheme, letter); According to modern studies, the performance of these functions is localized in the CNS mainly in the area of the temporal cortex, called Broca's Area, which was one of the last stages of human evolution.
- physiological mechanisms that ensure the actual implementation of speech utterance (the physical process of "speaking" or "writing").

The rules of language construction have ethno-specific features, which are expressed in the system of phonetic, lexical, grammatical and stylistic means and communication rules in a given language. Speech is closely integrated with all human mental processes. The linguistic side of human speech behavior is studied by psycholinguistics.

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